

THE ROLE OF OCB GREEN EMPLOYEES IN SUPPORTING THE IMPLEMENTATION OF THE SIGI GREEN REGIONAL REGULATION IN THE ENVIRONMENTAL SERVICE OF SIGI REGENCY

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Abstract

The implementation of local environmental policies is not solely determined by formal regulations, but also by the discretionary behavior of public employees as policy implementers. This study aims to analyze the role of Organizational Citizenship Behavior for the Environment (OCB Green) in supporting the implementation of Sigi Regency Regulation No. 4 of 2019 on Sigi Hijau at the Environmental Agency of Sigi Regency. A qualitative descriptive approach with a constructivist paradigm was employed. Data were collected through in-depth interviews, field observations, and document analysis involving eight informants selected using snowball sampling. Thematic analysis was conducted based on three OCB Green dimensions: eco-initiatives, eco-helping, and eco-civic engagement. The findings reveal that policy implementation is significantly strengthened by employees' extra-role behaviors. Eco-initiatives enhance internalization of environmental values, eco-helping reinforces a green organizational culture, and eco-civic engagement extends policy impacts to the community. These results indicate that OCB Green functions as an informal mechanism bridging formal policy and practical implementation, thereby improving the effectiveness of local environmental governance.

Keywords : *OCB Green, Environmental Policy, Public Organization, Pro-Environmental Behavior*

INTRODUCTION

The issues of sustainable development and environmental protection have become increasingly important global strategic agendas, including in the context of local government in Indonesia. Pressures on environmental quality resulting from population growth, urbanization, and environmentally unfriendly consumption patterns require local governments to not only formulate regulations but also ensure their effective implementation at the organizational and community levels. In this context, the success of environmental policies is not solely determined by the quality of regulations but also depends heavily on the behavior of officials implementing them on the ground. Sigi Regency, Central Sulawesi, responded to this challenge by enacting Sigi Regency Regulation Number 4 of 2019 concerning Green Sigi, which was reinforced by Regent Regulation Number 33 of 2023. This policy is designed to encourage environmentally conscious regional development through waste management, resource efficiency, reforestation, and increased community participation. The Sigi Regency Environmental Agency (DLH) is a regional agency with a strategic role in coordinating and implementing the Green Sigi policy.

However, the implementation of environmental policies at the regional level often faces structural challenges, such as limited budgets, human resources, and behavioral resistance from the public. This situation demonstrates that a regulatory approach alone is insufficient to ensure the success of environmental policies. Support from officials beyond formal duties is needed to ensure policies are internalized and effectively implemented in organizational and social practices. Field observations demonstrate the extra-role behavior of Sigi Regency Environmental Agency employees that supports the values of the Green Sigi policy. Employees voluntarily bring their own tumblers and lunch boxes, reduce the use of single-use plastics, turn off electricity and water when not in use, and manage organic waste through composting and eco-enzymes. Furthermore, there is evidence of cooperation among employees in cleaning and reforestation activities, as well as active involvement in environmental education for the community. These behaviors reflect Organizational Citizenship Behavior for the Environment (OCB Green), namely voluntary employee behavior that contributes to the environmental sustainability of the organization.

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In the management and public policy literature, Green OCB is understood as a crucial factor bridging formal policies with implementation practices. Previous research has shown that employees' extra-role behaviors contribute significantly to the effectiveness of green policies, both in the private and public sectors (Paillé & Mejía-Morelos, 2019). (Albrecht et al., 2022) However (Liu & Yu, 2023), empirical studies examining Green OCB in the context of local government in Indonesia, particularly in the implementation of environmental policies based on local regulations, are still relatively limited. Based on these conditions, this study aims to analyze the role of employees' OCB Green in supporting the effective implementation of Sigi Regency Regional Regulation Number 4 of 2019 concerning Green Sigi in the Sigi Regency Environmental Service. This study focuses on three main dimensions of OCB Green, namely eco-initiatives, eco-helping, and eco-civic engagement, as a framework for analyzing employee extra-role behavior in the context of regional public organizations.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Organizational Citizenship Behavior for the Environment (Green OCB)

Employee Extra-Role Behavior in supporting Environmental Policy is reflected through the concept of Organizational Citizenship Behavior for the Environment (OCB Green) (Wulandaru et al., 2024). In the context of Public Organizations, this behavior is an important element that shows the active involvement of employees to strengthen the implementation of green policies in the work environment.

OCB Green consists of three main dimensions:

1. Eco-Initiatives

describe employee initiatives to take environmentally friendly actions without waiting for instructions (Nurmadani & Waskito, 2025). In the context of the Sigi Regency Environmental Agency, this could include saving energy in the office, reducing the use of single-use plastics, using tumblers or personal cutlery, and making small innovations in internal waste management. These actions demonstrate employee awareness of the need to sustainably improve the work environment.

2. Eco-

Helping
Demonstrates Helping Behavior Employees participate in activities that support green policies. For example, helping colleagues participate in Clean Friday activities, reminding them not to litter, and working together to organize the office garden or the DLH green area. These behaviors strengthen solidarity and build a mutually supportive green work culture.

3. Eco- Civic Engagement

Reflecting employee participation beyond formal responsibilities in socio-environmental activities. DLH employees are frequently involved in tree planting, plastic waste reduction campaigns, and community composting training. This involvement extends the impact of the Green Sigi policy beyond the workplace to the social sphere.

These three dimensions show that OCB Green not only strengthens Internal Work Effectiveness, but also becomes an important instrument in measuring the success of implementing green policy values in the public sector.

Empirical Study

Previous studies strengthen the relevance of Green OCB to the effectiveness of environmental policies in the public sector:

1. Luu, (2019) researching OCB behavior Green leadership in the hospitality sector and found that green transformational leadership increases Eco-Initiatives and Eco- Helping through affective commitment to the environment. These results indicate that leadership that instills green values can encourage employee extra-role behavior.
2. Paillé et al., (2019) found that organizational commitment mediates the relationship between green policies and employee pro-environmental behavior. High commitment makes employees more consistent in demonstrating Eco-Initiatives and Eco- Civic Engagement.
3. Albrecht et al., (2022) revealed that environmentally oriented employee engagement contributes to increased Green Extra-Role behavior, especially in the Eco- Helping dimension, through the support of open organizational communication.
4. Liu & Yu, (2023) emphasizes the importance of a green organizational climate that strengthens the relationship between environmentally conscious leadership and Green OCB behavior. When the work climate supports environmental values, employees are more motivated to demonstrate Eco-Initiatives and Eco- Civic Behavior. engagement.

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These findings indicate that Green OCB behavior is a key indicator of the effectiveness of environmental policy implementation, both in the private and public sectors. In the context of the Sigi Regency Environmental Agency (DLH), extra-role employee behavior that supports the Sigi Green policy is a crucial factor in ensuring its implementation and sustainability.

Framework

Conditions at the Sigi Regency Environmental Agency indicate that the implementation of the Green Sigi policy is carried out through two approaches: institutional and employee behavior. From an institutional perspective, various programs have been developed, such as integrated waste management and area reforestation. However, the effectiveness of these policies depends heavily on the extent to which employees demonstrate extra-role behavior in supporting their implementation. Employees with Eco-Initiatives demonstrate their commitment through concrete actions such as conserving energy, using environmentally friendly products, and reducing waste in the office. Employees with Eco- Helping strengthen the spirit of cooperation through cleaning, greening activities, and reminding each other about green behavior. Meanwhile, Eco- Civic Engagement is seen from employee involvement in social and environmental activities with the community, such as waste management training or plastic reduction campaigns. Green Sigi policy implementation is measured by the extent to which these three dimensions are aligned within the DLH work culture. If employees demonstrate high levels of Green OCB, the values of the environmental policy will be more easily internalized and translated into concrete actions. (Boiral & Paillé, 2020). Thus, the aim of this study is to analyze the extra-role behavior of DLH employees through the dimensions of Eco-Initiatives, Eco- Helping, and Eco- Civic Engagement contributes to the effectiveness of the implementation of the Green Sigi policy in Sigi Regency.

RESEARCH METHODS

Study This use approach qualitative with paradigm constructivism (Robby Yana et al., 2024), which aim understand How behavior extra-role Sigi Regency Environmental Service (DLH) employees play a role in support effectiveness implementation Sigi Hijau Regional Regulation . This research focuses on three dimensions: **Eco-Initiatives**, concrete practices such as energy and water conservation, reducing single-use plastics, reusing items, and small innovations in office waste management carried out by employees. **Eco- Helping**, cooperation between employees in environmental cleanup activities, helping with the implementation of green programs, and reminding each other to maintain a clean and orderly work environment. **Eco- Civic Engagement**, Employee involvement in

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socio-environmental activities outside of formal duties, such as tree planting, community training, plastic waste reduction campaigns, and environmental education in the community.

Method of collecting data

In-depth Interview

Interviews were conducted to obtain information on employees' actual Green OCB practices in supporting the Green Sigi policy. Questions addressed three main dimensions:

1. Eco-Initiatives : personal initiatives to protect the environment.
2. Eco- Helping : cooperation and support between employees .
3. Eco- Civic Engagement : social-environmental involvement outside the office.

Interviews were conducted in a semi-structured manner so that researchers could explore the depth of data according to the context of employee behavior (Zebua et al., 2023).

Field Observation

Observations were conducted directly in the Sigi Regency Environmental Agency (DLH) work environment to record employee actions and habits that reflect Green OCB behavior . Observation results were recorded in observation sheets and field notes.

Documentation

Documentation was conducted by collecting various relevant documents to support the results of interviews and observations. The documents reviewed included:

1. Environmental activity reports, meeting minutes, and work program plans.
2. DLH internal archives relating to the implementation of the Green Sigi policy.
3. Photos of activities, publications, and environmental campaign materials.

documentary data serves as empirical evidence of the implementation of OCB Green behavior in the Sigi Regency DLH.

Research Instruments

The main instrument in this research is the researcher himself, who acts as a data collector, observer and analyzer. Researchers are equipped with:

1. OCB Green three-dimensional based interview guide ,
2. Field behavior observation sheet,
3. Voice recorder, camera, and field notebook to document data collection results.

Determination of Informants

Informants were determined using **the Snowball Sampling Technique** (Lenaini, 2021), starting from Main Officials to Implementing Employees who are active in Environmental Activities. Key informants consist of:

1. Head of the Sigi Regency Environmental Service,
2. Secretary of DLH,
3. Head of Cleaning Division,
4. Head of Pollution Control Division, and
5. Head of Environmental Compliance Division.

Next, additional informants will be determined based on the recommendations of the initial informants to deepen the required data.

Data Validity Test

Validity testing was carried out using **source and method triangulation**. (M. Husnullail et al., 2024), namely comparing the results of interviews, observations, and documentation to ensure data consistency. The validation process is carried out through:

1. Comparison between sources, to ensure the similarity of information,
2. Cross-checking the results of interviews and observations, as well as
3. Reconfirm with the informant (Member Checking) to ensure that the data interpretation is in accordance with the facts on the ground.

Data Analysis Techniques

The analysis was conducted using **a Thematic Approach** (Rozali, 2022), focusing on the actual actions of employees based on the three dimensions of Green OCB . The stages of the analysis include:

1. Identify employee behavior that reflects the dimensions of Eco-Initiatives, Eco- Helping , and Eco- Civic Engagement .
2. Grouping data based on dimension categories and policy implementation context.

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3. Analysis of supporting factors and obstacles to the emergence of Green OCB behavior in the DLH work environment.
4. Drawing conclusions regarding the contribution of each dimension of Green OCB to the effectiveness of the implementation of the Green Sigi policy.

The results of the analysis will be presented in the form of a thematic narrative that describes the relationship between employee extra-role behavior and the success of implementing environmental policy values in Sigi Regency.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Research Findings show that implementation Sigi Regency Regional Regulation Number 4 of 2019 concerning Green Sigi does not only executed through mechanism structural and formal programs, but relies heavily on behavioral extra-role Sigi Regency Environmental Agency employees . Behavior the manifested in a way real in three dimensions OCB Green, namely eco-initiatives, eco-helping, and eco-civic engagement. Summary findings study based on dimensions OCB Green is presented in Table 1.

Table 1 Summary Findings OCB Green in support Implementation Green Sigi policy

OCB Green Dimensions	Key Findings	Meaning for Policy Implementation
Eco-Initiatives	Employees voluntarily reduce single-use plastics, manage organic waste, save energy and water, and carry out simple 3R-based innovations in the office environment.	Strengthening the internalization of Green Sigi policy values at the individual level and supporting organizational resource efficiency.
Eco- Helping	Cooperation is formed between employees through routine cleaning activities, reminding each other about environmentally friendly behavior, and sharing responsibilities across fields.	Strengthening an environmentally friendly organizational culture and maintaining consistent policy implementation
Eco- Civic Engagement	Employees are actively involved in environmental education, waste bank development, greening activities, and partnerships with the community and stakeholders.	Expanding the impact of Green Sigi policies from the organizational environment to the community

Eco-Initiatives as a Form of Internalization of Environmental Policy

The eco- initiative dimension is reflected in various employee volunteer initiatives in support of the Sigi Hijau policy. Employees consistently bring their own tumblers and lunch boxes, reduce the use of single-use plastics, conserve energy and water, and utilize used materials for office facilities. Furthermore, employees are developing organic waste management through composting and eco- enzyme production within the office environment. This behavior indicates that environmental policy values have been internalized in employees' daily work practices. This finding aligns with (Paillé et al., 2019)the notion that eco- initiatives are a key indicator of the internalization of environmental values within an organization. In the public sector context, eco- initiatives are crucial because they can compensate for the budget and facility limitations often faced by local governments. The study (Luu, 2019)also confirmed that employee environmental initiatives contribute significantly to the sustainability of public organizations, especially when supported by exemplary leadership and conducive organizational norms. Thus, the Sigi Regency Environmental Agency's employee eco- initiatives serve as the foundation for implementing the Green Sigi policy internally.

Eco- Helping and Strengthening Environmentally Friendly Organizational Culture

The eco- helping dimension is realized through cooperation and support among employees in maintaining consistent implementation of environmental policies. Employees routinely engage in community service activities, reminding each other about waste management, electricity and water use, and maintaining smoke-free areas within the office. Sharing cleanliness responsibilities across departments also strengthens a sense of shared ownership of the work environment. These findings reinforce the view (Mi et al., 2020)that an environmentally friendly organizational culture is formed through social interactions and informal norms, not solely through written regulations. Eco- helping serves as a social mechanism that strengthens employee compliance and behavioral consistency with Sigi Hijau policies. However, the research also shows that differences in employee understanding of the policy's substance remain a challenge. This aligns with (Lee et al., 2023)the finding that the effectiveness of eco- helping is significantly

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influenced by employees' level of environmental policy literacy . Therefore, capacity building and internal education are crucial for maintaining the sustainability of eco- helping behavior .

Eco- Civic Engagement as an Expansion of Policy Impact to the Community

Eco- civic dimension Engagement is evident in the active involvement of Sigi Regency Environmental Agency (DLH) employees in various community-based environmental activities. Employees act as educators, mentors, and facilitators in waste bank development, 3R TPS management, Adiwiyata schools , and tree planting and environmental cleanup activities with the community. This behavior reflects the role of the apparatus as an agent of change that bridges regional policies with social practices in society. (Riyanto et al., 2024)) emphasizes that eco- civic Engagement expands the impact of environmental policies from the organizational realm to the social realm, thereby enhancing the long-term sustainability of policies.

OCB Green as a Key Factor in Policy Implementation Effectiveness

The synthesis of research results shows that OCB Green plays a key role in bridging formal policy and the implementation practices of the Sigi Green Regional Regulation. Eco- initiatives strengthen the internalization of environmental values at the individual level, eco- helping maintains consistency through internal social mechanisms, and eco- civic engagement extends the impact of policies to the community.

CONCLUSION

Based on the results of the research and discussion, it can be concluded that the success of the implementation of Sigi Regency Regional Regulation Number 4 of 2019 concerning Green Sigi is not only determined by the existence of institutional regulations and programs, but is greatly influenced by the extra-role behavior of employees that reflects Organizational Citizenship Behavior for the Environment (OCB Green). In the context of the Sigi Regency Environmental Agency, OCB Green has proven to be an informal mechanism that bridges environmental policies with implementation practices in the field. The eco- initiatives dimension demonstrates that employees voluntarily internalize environmental policy values through initiatives to reduce plastic waste, improve energy and water efficiency, manage organic waste, and innovate in the use of used goods. This behavior indicates that the Green Sigi policy is not merely understood as an administrative obligation but has become part of employee awareness and work habits. Eco- initiatives serve as an internal foundation for policy implementation, particularly in the face of limited organizational resources.

The eco- helping dimension demonstrates the crucial role of social interaction and organizational culture in maintaining consistent environmental policy implementation. Cooperation, mutual reminders, and shared responsibility for cleaning among employees strengthen internal adherence to the values of the Sigi Hijau policy. Eco- helping reflects not only individual behavior but also demonstrates the formation of an environmentally friendly organizational culture that supports the collective sustainability of the policy. Meanwhile, the eco- civic dimension Engagement emphasizes the role of Sigi Regency Environmental Agency employees as agents of change, bridging regional policies with the community. Employee involvement in environmental education, waste bank development, 3R waste disposal site (TPS 3R) management, Adiwiyata schools, and multi-stakeholder partnerships extends the impact of the Green Sigi policy from the organizational level to the social realm. This dimension is crucial because the success of regional environmental policies depends heavily on changes in community behavior. Overall, this study confirms that Green OCB is a key factor in the effective implementation of regional environmental policies. Green OCB serves not merely as a supporting behavior but as a crucial prerequisite for the implementation of Green Sigi policies in a concrete, sustainable, and impactful manner. These findings enrich the study of Green OCB in the context of the public sector, particularly local government in Indonesia, which has so far been relatively limited.

Practical Implications

The results of this study provide practical implications: strengthening the implementation of the Green Sigi policy needs to be directed not only at improving regulations and formal programs, but also at establishing a work culture that encourages the emergence of Green OCB behaviors. Leadership role models, ongoing internal education, and institutional support are crucial factors in maintaining consistent employee environmentally friendly behavior.

Suggestion

Practical Advice (Policy and Organization)

1. The Sigi Regency Environmental Service needs to strengthen the internalization of the Green Sigi policy through ongoing education and outreach programs for all employees, so that understanding of the substance of the policy becomes more evenly distributed.

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2. Organizational leaders are expected to provide real role models in environmentally friendly practices, because leadership behavior has been proven to encourage the emergence of Green OCB in employees.
3. multi-stakeholder partnerships with village governments, schools, communities, and non-governmental organizations needs to be continuously developed to expand the impact of the Green Sigi policy in the community.
4. The approach to changing organizational culture needs to be prioritized by making environmentally friendly behavior a collective habit, not just a response to a particular program.

Academic Advice

1. Further research can examine OCB Green in other local government contexts to broaden the generalizability of the findings.
2. Further studies are suggested using a quantitative or mixed methods approach to test the causal relationship between Green OCB, leadership, and environmental policy performance.

Future research could also explore the role of institutional factors and organizational culture in strengthening the sustainability of Green OCB behavior in the public sector.

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